

Description of *Cruzia sanjuanensis* sp. nov. (Cosmocercoidea: Kathlaniidae) in the tortoise *Chelonoidis chilensis* (Testudines: Testudinidae) in the province of San Juan, Argentina

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<https://zoobank.org/FBB2B62D-B9D7-4BEA-A3EF-C4A9FB93109C>

Abstract: A new species of *Cruzia* (Cosmocercoidea: Kathlaniidae) collected from the large intestine of the tortoise (*Chelonoidis chilensis*) in the province of San Juan, Argentina is described. The new species differs from the rest of the species assigned to *Cruzia* by: number of tooth-like structures, position of the vulva and size. *Cruzia sanjuanensis* sp. nov. has 13–16 teeth per row, and the vulva position is equatorial. These characters differentiate it from other Neotropical species such as *Cruzia lauroi* with 12 teeth per row and a pre-equatorial vulva, and *Cruzia rudolphi* and *Cruzia boliviana* both with 16–18 teeth per row. The new species represents the eleventh species of *Cruzia* and the first described for a reptile in Argentina.

Keywords: Argentina, nematodes, parasites, San Juan

Introduction

The tortoise *Chelonoidis chilensis* Gray, 1870 (Testudines: Testudinidae) has a wide distribution in different provinces of Argentina (Acosta et al., 2017; Stazzonelli et al., 2020). The loss of habitat due to the expansion of the agricultural frontier, and the consequent loss and modification of the environment, along with the commercial and illegal extraction, makes this tortoise species categorised as vulnerable by IUCN (Stazzonelli et al., 2020). They feed on stems, cacti fruits, grasses and leguminous pods. They are solitary, territorial and oviparous (Acosta et al., 2017). Parasitological records and studies are scarce, probably due to its state of conservation and

protection, which is difficult to analyse (González-Rivas et al., 2019).

So far, the few existing records are related to nematodes of the genera *Labiduris* Schneider, 1866 (Cosmocercoidea: Atractidae) and *Falcaustra* Lane, 1915 (Cosmocercoidea: Kathlaniidae) found in the large intestine (González-Rivas et al., 2019; Castillo et al., 2020).

The nematodes of the genus *Cruzia* Travassos, 1917 (Cosmocercoidea: Kathlaniidae) are parasites of amphibians, reptiles and mammals, and present certain characteristics that differentiate them from rest of the genera of the family Kathlaniidae: the presence of three articulated triangular lips and well-defined denticles in the pharyngeal part of the

Fig. 1. Type locality of *Cruzia sanjuanensis* sp. nov. in the tortoise *Chelonoidis chilensis*. (A) South America, (B) Argentina, (C) San Juan province, Rivadavia Department (red star).

esophagus (Anderson et al., 2009). Some species of *Cruzia* require more detailed taxonomic studies and should be re-evaluated, since existing studies do not provide data on them (Vieira et al., 2020).

Vieira et al. (2020) mention 10 species of the genus *Cruzia*: *Cruzia americana* Maplestone, 1930; *Cruzia boliviana* Sprehn, 1932; *Cruzia cameroni* Wolfgang, 1951; *Cruzia buckleyi* Wahid, 1964; *Cruzia brasiliensis* Costa, 1965; *Cruzia tropidodipsi* Ubelaker & Younus, 1965; *Cruzia empera* Guerrero, 1971; *Cruzia rudolphi* Ruiz, 1947; *Cruzia tentaculata* Rudolphi, 1819; and *Cruzia lauroi* Vieira, Gonçalves, de Souza Lima, de Sousa & Muniz-Pereira, 2020. All these species belong to the Neotropical region, except for *C. americana* described in *Didelphis marsupialis* Linnaeus, 1758, collected in the United States (Crites, 1956; Vieira et al., 2020).

Of all the mentioned species in the Neotropical region, three are parasites in reptiles: *C. rudolphi* in *Erythrolamprus aesculapii* Linnaeus, 1758 collected

in Brazil; *C. tropidodipsi* in *Tropidodipsas fasciata* Günther, 1858 collected in México; and *C. lauroi* in *Salvator merianae* Duméril and Bibron 1839 collected in Brazil (Ruiz 1947; Ubelaker & Younus, 1965; Vieira et al., 2020).

In the present study, a new species of nematode of the genus *Cruzia* is described, parasitising the tortoise *C. chilensis*, for the province of San Juan, Argentina.

Material and methods

In November 2018, a terrestrial tortoise *C. chilensis* (female; carapace length 19 cm) obtained from the Center for Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education and Responsible Recreation located in the department of Rivadavia, San Juan Province, Argentina (Parque Faunístico: 31°30'19.99"S, 68°38'40.45"W) was necropsied (Fig. 1). The specimen had died of unknown causes. The body cavity

Fig. 2. *Chelonoidis chilensis* turtle from the Center for Rehabilitation for Wildlife, Environmental Education and Responsible Recreation (Fauna Park), Rivadavia Department, San Juan Province, Argentina.

was opened through a mid-ventral incision, and the digestive tract was removed and examined with a stereoscopic binocular microscope. The nematodes found alive were stored in 70% ethanol. For the observation of the nematodes, semi-permanent preparations were made using lactophenol solution. The identification was carried out using a light microscope (Arcano Xsp optical binocular). The specimens were deposited in the Parasitological Collection of the Center for Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education and Responsible Recreation (Parque Faunístico) (Code: CRFSJ_P_01). Drawings were made using a camera lucida attached to a light microscope. The parasite ecological indicators were calculated based on the definitions of Bush et al. (1997). Measurements are in μm , with mean ± 1 SD and range in parentheses unless otherwise noted.

Results

Fifteen adult nematodes (10 females and 5 males) were collected from the large intestine of a male *Chelonoidis chilensis* (Fig. 2).

Description

Family Kathlaniidae (Lane, 1914)

Subfamily Cruzeinae (Travassos, 1917)

Cruzia sanjuanensis sp. nov. (Fig. 3)

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General: Medium-sized nematodes, white with a straight and thick body, evident sexual dimorphism, males smaller than females. Thick cuticle. Mouth surrounded by three articulated triangular lips, with the presence of papillae on them (Fig. 3D). The dorsal lip has a pair of papillae, and the lateral lips have one papilla and one aphid each (Fig. 3D). The new species (males and females) presents a total of 13–16 teeth per row (Fig. 3B). Presence of intestinal diverticulum projected towards the anterior region, thick and occupying approximately a quarter of the length of the esophagus. The esophagus is divided into four parts: a pharynx with three columns of tooth-like

Fig. 3. *Cruzia sanjuanensis* sp. nov. (A, B, C) male anterior region, lateral view, toothed structures are visible; (D) lips with papillae. p = papillae, a = aphid, ld = dorsal lip, ll = lateral lip, t = 13–16 teeth per row, d = intestinal diverticulum, e = esophagus, ph = pharynx, eb = esophageal bulb, pbs = prebulbar structure, nr = nerve ring, ep = excretory pore.

structures, a long body, a short prebulbar structure, and an esophageal bulb. Both males and females have a short tail.

Males (based on 4 adult specimens) (μm): Total body length 12144 ± 1150 (11123–13620), maximum width 768 ± 65 (681–839). Esophageal length 3047 ± 122 (2882–3178), bulb length 357 ± 95 (227–454), bulb width 353 ± 26 (340–392). Distance to the nerve ring 616 ± 21 (588–637) and distance to the excretory pore 1925 ± 17 (1900–1938) from the front. Presence of a pair of equal spicules, of medium size, with a length of 542 ± 95 (490–686) and some curvature is observed. Tail length 58.7 ± 3.5 (55–63). It presents three pairs of pre-cloacal papillae, three pairs of ad-cloacal papillae and four pairs of post-cloacal papillae, as well as an unpaired papilla on the anterior edge of the cloacal opening (3+1:3:4).

Females (based on 4 adult specimens) (μm): Total body length 15010 ± 1251 (13166–15890), maximum width 802 ± 73 (735–908), esophageal length 3685 ± 309 (3223–3859), and bulb length 443 ± 71 (340–

490), bulb width 330 ± 33 (295–372). Distance to nerve ring 701 ± 61 (637–784) and to the equatorial vulva 6797 ± 34 (6750–6830) from the front. The eggs are elliptical in shape, with a length of 91.6 ± 10.4 (80–100) and an egg width of 47.6 ± 2.5 (45–50).

Taxonomic summary

Host: *Chelonoidis chilensis*.

Type locality: Department of Rivadavia, San Juan Province, Argentina. Center for Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education and Responsible Recreation (Parque Faunístico $31^{\circ}30'19.99''\text{S}$, $68^{\circ}38'40.45''\text{W}$).

Infection site: Large intestine.

Type series: Male holotype, CRFSJ_P_01A, female paratype, CRFSJ_P_01B

Intensity: 15 nematodes.

Etymology: The name of the new species refers to the province where it was recorded (San Juan Province, Argentina).

Table 1. Morphological measurements (mm) of males for *Cruzia* Neotropical species.

	<i>Cruzia tentaculata</i> (Rudolphi, 1819)	<i>Cruzia rudolphi</i> Ruiz, 1947	<i>Cruzia cameroni</i> Wolfgang, 1951	<i>Cruzia buckleyi</i> Wahid, 1964	<i>Cruzia tropidodipsi</i> Ubelaker & Younus, 1965	<i>Cruzia brasiliensis</i> Costa, 1965	<i>Cruzia lauroi</i> Vieira, Gonçalves, de Souza Lima, de Sousa & Muniz-Pereira, 2020	<i>Cruzia sanjuanensis</i> sp. nov.
Body length	11.00–12.05	14	12.7–13.7	11–12	6.70–8.60	9.6–15.7	6.60–8.82	11.1–12.4
Maximum width	0.53–0.65	0.39	0.48–0.54	0.5–0.57	0.38–0.5	0.52–0.7	0.33–0.37	0.68–0.83
Pharynx length	–	0.18	–	0.09–0.1	0.21–0.26	0.15–0.27	0.09–0.15	0.25–0.27
Esophageal length	2.07–2.32	1.8	2.4–2.7	1.57–1.7	–	1.99–2.75	1.3–1.95	2.88–3.17
Bulb length	0.29–0.32	0.27	–	0.3–0.33	0.23–0.30	0.27–0.35	0.2–0.31	0.22–0.45
Bulb width	0.27–0.33	–	–	–	0.27–0.30	0.28–0.4	0.2–0.3	0.34–0.39
Intestinal length	0.37–0.42	–	0.06–0.99	0.75–0.9	0.63–0.92	0.48–0.84	0.55–0.85	0.7–0.79
Distance to the nerve ring	0.48–0.55	0.49	0.54–0.63	–	0.50–0.60	0.49–0.62	0.26–0.48	0.58–0.63
Distance to the excretory pore	1.18–1.30	–	1.08–1.26	0.83	1.31–1.6	–	0.77–0.93	1.9–1.93
Spicules length	0.89–0.96	0.49	1.17–1.27	1.5–1.7	0.76–1.21	0.7–0.96	0.60–0.75	0.49–0.68

Table 2. Morphological measurements (mm) of females for *Cruzia* Neotropical species.

	<i>Cruzia tentaculata</i> (Rudolphi, 1819)	<i>Cruzia rudolphi</i> Ruiz, 1947	<i>Cruzia cameroni</i> Wolfgang, 1951	<i>Cruzia buckleyi</i> Wahid, 1964	<i>Cruzia tropidodipsi</i> Ubelaker & Younus, 1965	<i>Cruzia brasiliensis</i> Costa, 1965	<i>Cruzia lauroi</i> Vieira, Gonçalves, de Souza Lima, de Sousa & Muniz-Pereira, 2020	<i>Cruzia sanjuanensis</i> sp. nov.
Body length	11.40–12.20	16.2	9.15–18.25	15–17	7.79–9.66	14.16–18.4	8.21–9.75	13.16–15.8
Maximum width	0.50–0.55	0.46	0.41–0.65	0.5–0.5	0.41–0.57	0.52–0.70	0.37–0.45	0.73–0.90
Pharynx length	–	0.17	–	0.11	0.21–0.24	0.21–0.28	0.14–0.20	0.25–0.32
Esophageal length	1.59–2.16	1.80	2.1–2.3	1.83–1.93	–	2.21–2.88	1.56–2	3.22–3.85
Bulb length	0.25–0.27	–	–	0.35–0.42	0.26–0.30	0.28–0.33	0.27–0.33	0.34–0.49
Bulb width	0.25–0.32	–	–	–	0.27–0.33	0.31–0.43	0.28–0.33	0.29–0.37
Intestinal length	0.39–0.45	–	–	0.92	0.72–1.09	0.49–0.92	0.47–0.98	0.79–0.98
Distance to the nerve ring	0.48–0.55	–	–	–	0.50–0.57	0.49–0.67	0.26–0.42	0.63–0.78
Distance to the excretory pore	1.18–1.30	–	–	1.1	1.21–1.3	–	0.87–0.92	–
Distance to the vulva	5.54–5.83	8.0	–	6	4.53–5.29	6.79–10.08	1.71–2.17	6.75–6.83

Discussion

The genus *Cruzia* has rarely been recorded, being little studied, requiring more investigations and detailed

studies. A total of 9 species of the genus *Cruzia* are found in the Neotropical Region: *C. boliviana*, *C. cameroni*, *C. buckleyi*, *C. brasiliensis*, *C. tropidodipsi*, *C. empera*, *C. rudolphi*, *C. tentaculata* and *C.*

Table 3. Comparison of some taxonomic characters for Neotropical *Cruzia* species.

	Numbers of tooth-like structures	Caudal papillae	Vulvar position	Host	References
<i>Cruzia tentaculata</i> (Rudolphi, 1819)	10	3:3:4	Equatorial	<i>Didelphis marsupialis</i> (mammal, marsupial)	Adnet, Anjos, Menezes-Oliveira & Lanfredi, 2009
<i>Cruzia boliviana</i> Sprehn, 1932	16–18 (25)	3:3:4	Pre-equatorial	<i>Tolipeutes novencinctus</i> (mammal, cingulate)	Sprehn 1932; Schuurmans-Stekhoven, 1950
<i>Cruzia rudolphi</i> Ruiz, 1947	16–18	3:3:4	Equatorial	<i>Erythrolamprus aesculapii</i> (snake)	Vicente, Oliveira Rodrigues, Corrêa Gomes & Magalhães Pinto, 1993
<i>Cruzia cameroni</i> Wolfgang, 1951	13–17	3:3:4	Equatorial	<i>Didelphis marsupialis</i> (mammal, marsupial)	Wolfgang, 1951
<i>Cruzia buckleyi</i> Wahid, 1964	6–7	3:2:4	Post-equatorial	<i>Callimico goeldii</i> (mammal, primate)	Wahid, 1964
<i>Cruzia tropidodipsi</i> Ubelaker & Younus, 1965	13–14	3:3:4	Post-equatorial	<i>Tropidodipsas fasciata</i> (reptile, snake)	Ubelaker & Younus, 1965
<i>Cruzia brasiliensis</i> Costa, 1965	17–22	3:3:5	Pre-equatorial	<i>Sus scrofa</i> = (<i>Sus domesticus</i>) (mammal, domestic pig)	Costa, 1965
<i>Cruzia lauroi</i> Vieira, Gonçalves, de Souza Lima, de Sousa & Muniz-Pereira, 2020	12	3:3:4	Pre-equatorial	<i>Salvator merianae</i> (reptile, lizard)	Vieira, Gonçalves, de Souza Lima, de Sousa & Muniz-Pereira, 2020
<i>Cruzia sanjuanensis</i> sp. nov.	13–16	3:3:4	Equatorial	<i>Chelonoidis chilensis</i> (reptile, turtle)	current publication

lauroi (Vieira et al., 2020). In general, there is little information and knowledge of this genus, except for original descriptions such as Sprehn (1932), Wolfgang (1951), Wahid (1964), Coast (1965), Ubelaker & Younus (1965), Guerrero (1971), Ruiz (1947) and Vieira et al. (2020), and some references that mention the genus in Brazil such as Vicente et al. (1990, 1993, 1997), Boero & Boehringer (1967) in Argentina, and Mollericonna & Nallar (2014) in Bolivia. This means that the information provided in this work comes up with new knowledge about this genus of parasites in the Neotropics.

The main characters that allow differentiating *Cruzia* species in the Neotropics are: specimen sizes, number of tooth-like structures, number of caudal papillae in males, size of spicules, and position of the vulva in the body (equatorial, pre-equatorial, and post-equatorial) (Vieira et al., 2020). We found variation and similarities in sizes of males and females for the morphometric characters measured with respect to other *Cruzia* species from the Neotropics (Tables 1,

2). However, in the different species of *Cruzia*, the number of tooth like structures per row of the internal pharynx is the main characteristic that allows distinguishing the different species (Vieira et al., 2020). The newly found species *C. sanjuanensis* presents between 13–16 teeth per row, differing from *C. boliviana* with 16–18, *C. buckleyi* with 6–7, *C. brasiliensis* with 17–22, *C. empera* with 9, *C. rudolphi* with 16–18, *C. tentaculata* with 10 and *C. lauroi* with 12 teeth per row respectively.

The new species *C. sanjuanensis* is similar to *C. cameroni* with 13–17 teeth, and *C. tropidodipsi* with 13–14 teeth per row, respectively. However, *C. sanjuanensis* differs from *C. cameroni* and *C. tropidodipsi* in spicule size, vulva position and geographic distribution. *Cruzia sanjuanensis* has a spicule size of 0.49–0.68 mm, a character that differentiates it from *C. cameroni* with a spicule of 1.17–1.27 mm, and the vulva of *C. sanjuanensis* is in an equatorial position, whereas the vulva position of *C. tropidodipsi* is post-equatorial (see Table 3).

Fig. 4. *Cruzia sanjuanensis* sp. nov. (A, B, C) male posterior region, spicules are observed, pre and postcloacal papillae; (A, B) ventral view, details of ad-cloacal and post-cloacal papillae, furthermore an unpaired papilla at the anterior edge of the cloacal opening; (C) lateral view; (D) female posterior region; (E) egg. sp = spicules; tl = tail; prp = pre-cloacal papillae; adp = three pairs of ad-cloacal papillae; psp = pairs of post-cloacal papillae; up = unpaired papilla, eg = eggs.

Regarding the position and number of papillae, *C. sanjuanensis* presents three pairs of pre-cloacal papillae, three ad-cloacal pairs and four post-cloacal pairs, as well as an unpaired papilla on the anterior edge of the cloacal opening (Fig. 4). Taking into account the distribution of papillae, except for *C. brasiliensis* and *C. buckleyi* which present a 3:3:5 and 3:2:4 distribution, the rest of the species mentioned for the Neotropics have a 3:3:4 distribution (Vieira et al., 2020). The presence of an unpaired papilla in *C. sanjuanensis* differentiates it from *C. cameroni*, *C. empera* and *C. tropidodipsi* (Wolfgang, 1951; Guerrero, 1971; Ubelaker & Younus, 1965; Vieira et al., 2020).

In Argentina, up to now, species of the genus *Cruzia* have not been mentioned in reptiles (Castillo et al., 2020) and in mammals only *Cruzia tentaculata* has been mentioned parasitising *Didelphis albiventris* (Boero & Boehringer, 1967; Fugassa, 2020).

Our work describes a new species of nematode of the genus *Cruzia* found in the intestine of the tortoise

C. chilensis. Such specimen belonged to the Center for Rehabilitation for Wildlife, Environmental Education and Responsible Recreation (Parque Faunístico) located in the department of Rivadavia, province of San Juan, Argentina. The scarce information and records of this genus of nematodes make this work relevant for future comparative studies in other types of hosts. This work is the first mention of the genus parasitising a tortoise in the Neotropics, since five species have been recorded in mammals and two in snakes, one in a lizard and one in an amphibian (Vieira et al., 2020).

Acknowledgements

We thank authorities and intendant of the Municipality of Rivadavia, San Juan province. We also thank Faunístico: Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education and Responsible Recreation Center. We

thank Agostina González-Rivas assisted us in drafting the English version. The authors declare no competing interests.

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